

ASSESSMENT OF ZEOLITE USE FOR REMOVAL OF PETROLEUM COMPOUNDS FROM WASTEWATER

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ABSTRACT. Zeolites are types of inorganic porous materials that have been widely investigated and applied for their excellent sorption ability for wastewater treatment. Their low cost, safeness, natural abundance and accessibility make them good candidates for a large-scale application. Pollution generated by organic compounds, especially hydrocarbons from oil spills and crude oil refineries emerge as a great concern for aquatic life and the environment. The hydrophobic and highly stable molecules of hydrocarbons determine their persistence toward conventional methods involved in water treatment plants and accidental spills in oceans and seas. This paper presents the works that have been focused on implementation of natural and synthetic zeolites and their modified forms as well as zeolite composites for removal of hydrocarbons from wastewater.

Key words: zeolites; wastewater treatment; oil spill; hydrocarbon pollution

Introduction

The treatment of water, aimed at removing various chemical components or mixtures, is an issue that occupies an increasingly important place in modern science and technology. The search for effective, cheap and easy-to-do methods for the removal of toxic and biologically hazardous substances is also necessitated by the rapid development of industry and the consumption of raw materials. For example, different types of sorbents - natural, synthetic, organic and inorganic, have been tested and investigated as possible materials for oil removal (Rajaković-Ognjanović et al., 2007).

Zeolites are naturally occurring aluminosilicates characterised by their microporous crystalline structure consisting of a great number of pores of uniform shape and size arranged in three dimensional structures. The pore size of zeolites can vary based on their type, origin and method of synthesis, that can be estimated average in the range of 2–13 Å, which puts them in the scope of molecule size of a great number of compounds. This fact predetermines their use for selective separation of chemicals based on molecular size and shape exclusion, functioning as molecular sieves for many applications. Such examples include an industrial scale process of separation and drying of gasses and solvents. They can be implemented in the separation of different structural isomers of aliphatic hydrocarbons (Laredo et al., 2013), aromatics (Methivier, 2002) and nuclear waste and leak management (Breck, 1974; Liebau et al., 1998). The chemically and mechanically resistant structure of the zeolites makes them very suitable for catalysts in corrosive media (strongly basic or acidic) at high temperatures and pressures since they do not undergo destruction and can be utilised in recycling processes (Kadja et al., 2022). A number of different applications have been reported regarding their sorption properties for removal of both organic and inorganic pollutants (de Peña et al., 2000; Franus and Wdowin, 2010; Chaouati et al., 2013; Ping et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2020; de Magalhães et al., 2022) due to their highly developed surface, porosity, molecular dimensions of the pores, surface functional groups,

high adsorption capacity and partitioning of reactants and products (Corma, 2003).

Zeolites are widely used in acid catalysed large-scale petrochemical processes such as isomerization, alkylation, thermal cracking in petroleum refining and parallel to that in fine chemicals synthesis, biomass conversion and CO₂ utilisation (Zhang et al., 2022). These properties are largely determined by the pore sizes of different zeolite types, highly influencing their sorption and sieving properties. That makes the prospect of control over the structure, crystal size and morphology of the existing natural zeolites or synthetic ones of utmost importance. It was reported that an attempt to tune the pore aperture size of the engineered zeolite was performed to improve its selectivity in separation processes (Vansant, 1990; Palčić and Valtchev, 2020).

Petrochemicals hold the major share of the fuel market and strategic resources in the world economy. Since crude oil and gas are drilled in few parts of the world but utilised all over, that requires transport, storage and application which inevitably leads to the probability of chemical spills. Such events result in substantial environmental hazard and economic losses (Carmody et al., 2008). Unfortunately, several such accidents at open sea have been reported (Lucien et al., 2004; Zuberogoitia et al., 2006). These events have a devastating effect on aquatic life and their periodic occurrence prompts for development of potential adsorbent materials suitable for damage control (Bandura et al., 2015). In removal of oil spills, mineral inorganic (zeolites, clays, silica-based minerals) and natural organic (leaves, peat, moss, wood, cotton) adsorbents as well as polymers are used (Bandura et al., 2017).

Besides the large amount of oil, the chemical composition of petroleum pollutants makes the spills very difficult to be removed and treated effectively. They consist mainly of organic compounds which are very stable and highly hydrophobic like aliphatic (C_nH_{2n+2}), naphthenic (i.e. cycloalkanes) and aromatic hydrocarbons (Liu et al., 2015). Special consideration should be paid to the aromatic monocyclic hydrocarbons - with high toxicity commonly denoted as BTEX - benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene (Baltrėnas et al., 2011) which are the subject of numerous attempts to be removed. Additional issue

that can arise is the possibility of migration of petrochemicals and further contamination of air, soil and ground water.

The utilisation of zeolites as effective sorbents for oil spills is a tempting prospect. Studies demonstrating optimistic results on the sorption capacity of zeolites and organo-modified zeolites in the removal of BTEX and the removal of other aromatic hydrocarbons from contaminated water have been published (Wang et al., 2010).

Natural zeolites

Many reports reveal that natural zeolites are not the most obvious choice when it comes to treatment of organic / oil pollutants by sorption. Since the hydrocarbons are hydrophobic, non-polar and immiscible in water, while the zeolites' surface is negatively charged, it is not to be expected that zeolites will attract the organic molecules strongly to their surface thus enabling sorption as a method of removal (Corma, 2003). As their surface is negatively charged, the zeolites strongly attract positively charged species like heavy metal ions and are widely used for their removal (Inglezakis et al., 2002; Wang, et al., 2010).

However, being a very convenient perspective as sorbents, attempts have been made and researchers continue to search for natural zeolites to be applied as effective adsorbents in water treatment and removal of hydrocarbons from oil polluted water. For example, Kalbuadi et al. studied the use of clinoptilolite-based zeolite for crude oil spill removal from sea water (2019).

Yousef et al. (2011) reported the effect of different parameters on the sorption of phenol (component of crude oil) onto Jordanian zeolitic tuff (from Jabal Aritayn). Initially the adsorption rate was high and the amount of phenol onto the zeolite surface increased steadily within 2 h of adsorption. During this time, the adsorption uptake for 10, 30, 50, 70, and 90 mg/l phenol solutions is found to be 96 %, 88 %, 86 %, 76 %, and 84 %, respectively. The decrease of adsorption with the increase of phenol concentration was attributed to the repulsion among phenol molecules attached to the zeolite surface in the bulk phase. It was determined that the pseudo-second-order model fitted best the sorption kinetics and the best-fitted adsorption isotherm models were found to be in the order: Freundlich > Redlich–Peterson > Langmuir > Temkin for temperature range 25–45 °C. The experimental data suggested that the intraparticle diffusion is not the rate limiting step in the phenol adsorption process. Using the Langmuir model and the experimental data the maximum adsorption capacity of 34.5, 24.9, 23.8, and 23.3 mg/g was determined correspondingly at 25, 35, 45, and 55 °C. Thermodynamically, it was determined that the adsorption of phenol onto zeolite is a physical process with enthalpy change $\Delta H^\circ = -10.2$ kJ/mol.

Khader et al. (2021) studied the adsorption of oil compounds and chemical oxygen demand (COD) reduction from oily produced water by several adsorbents (activated carbon, zeolite, silica gel). The mixed adsorbent (activated carbon and silica gel) demonstrated the highest adsorption capacity, while the zeolite showed moderate performance.

V. Rajaković-Ognjanović et al. (2008) compared two types of sorbents, organic and inorganic, for removal of motor oil - and a zeolite from Serbia was one of the tested inorganic materials. The summarised results showed that organic type of sorbents, namely natural wool fibres (NWF) and recycled-wool-based nonwoven material (RNWM) were more efficient

sorbents with maximal efficiency and maximal sorption capacity as follows: 0.1 g of NWFs in 10 min at 20 °C and pH 8.00 sorbed 3.3 g of motor oil from 300 ml of water polluted with 4.5 g of motor oil. Maximal efficiency for all sorbents investigated was reached in 30 min of sorption processes, it was 95.0 % for NWF, 43.0 % for NRWM, 20.7 % for sepiolite, 19.6 % for bentonite and 21.2 % for zeolite. Difference in the behaviour regarding efficiency of oil removal with sepiolite and zeolite was observed - it increased with increasing the pH value. For bentonite the efficiency decreased with the pH raise. The optimal removal (21 %) for zeolite was achieved at pH value 10.00 while minimum efficiency zeolite exhibited at pH 5.00 (18 %). These data clearly demonstrated that organic materials have much higher sorption capacity towards motor oil than the inorganic ones. Nevertheless, inorganic materials worth to be further investigated for application in oil removal, due to their positive features like thermal and mechanical stability.

Modified zeolites

In order to overcome the weaknesses in the adsorption performance of natural zeolites, they can be modified by making their surface more hydrophobic. For this purpose, the most used approach involves immobilisation of surfactants from the group of quaternary ammonium salts onto the zeolites (Simpson et al., 2009; Sakthivel et al., 2013). This kind of functionalisation of zeolite structure would change the character of a zeolite surface from hydrophilic to hydrophobic and would render for increasing its affinity towards organic pollutants. The process usually involves exchange of cation from the zeolite surface (Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , etc.) with a long-chain organic cation. One of the most typically used quaternary ammonium salts is the hexadecyl-trimethyl-ammonium bromide (HDTMA-Br). Investigations on the use of these types of compounds for both natural and synthetic zeolites modifications were reported (Vidal et al. 2012; Muir and Bajda 2016; Muir et al., 2016). HDTMA-Br and other organic cations are attracted to the zeolite surface due to electrostatic forces of attraction. Thus, the organo-modified zeolites possess a hydrophobic surface and could potentially acquire improved sorption properties toward petroleum products such as oils and BTEX compounds (Ranck et al., 2005; Carmody et al., 2007).

Bandura et al. (2015) determined sorption capacity (SC, g/g) of three types of sorbents by weighing the sorbent before and after saturation with the petroleum substance. The following equation was applied for data processing and estimation:

$$SC = (M - M_0)/M_0 \quad (1)$$

where M is the weight of the sorbent after sorption of petroleum product, and M_0 is the weight of the sorbent before sorption. SC of clinoptilolite (Sokirnica Mine, Ukraine), diatomite (commercially available sorbent Absodan), and zeolites synthesised from fly ash (Na-P1 and Na-X type) towards diesel and biodiesel oils was determined using glass columns filled with sorbent ($d = 1$ cm), dropped by the oil and left to the bed saturation.

Muir et al. (2016) conducted a detailed study involving powdered zeolites and organo-zeolites towards petrol, diesel, engine oil, and used engine oil. Clinoptilolite (Cp) (Sokirnica Mine) and zeolite Na-P1, produced by the hydrothermal synthesis of F-class fly ash obtained from the Rybnik power

plant in Poland were modified with 8 different surfactants: octadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (ODTMA), hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (HDTMA), tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide (TDTMA), dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide (DDTMA), dioctadecyldimethylammonium bromide (DODDMA), dihexadecyldimethylammonium bromide (DHDDMA), ditetradecyldimethylammonium bromide (DTDDMA) and didodecyldimethylammonium bromide (DDDDMA), all of them belonging to the quaternary ammonium salts. The estimated sizes of zeolite P1 and clinoptilolite pores (4.5–7.0 Å) are smaller than the surfactants' particle size (over 10 Å), so that the organic cations are too large to enter the zeolite channels. This means that the modification process takes place only on the external zeolite surface, where most of the active sites of the zeolite are located. It was determined experimentally that the external cation exchange capacities (ECEC) for Cp was 11.45 meq/100 g of HDTMA ions, while for Na-P1 it was 24.40 meq/100 g. The experiments conducted to evaluate the sorption efficiency showed very interesting patterns - in the case of natural zeolite, the longer the carbon chain of the surfactant is, the more effective is the modification. This was not the case for zeolite Na-P1 using these salts. Although the degree of modification is higher, there is no clear effect of the carbon chain length on the modification process. The sorption studies that were conducted on petroleum compounds demonstrated that a synthetic zeolite Na-P1 and its modifications have much higher affinity towards petrochemicals compared to the natural zeolite clinoptilolite and Cp-organo-zeolites. These differences can be explained by the different degree of modification and surface area available. The most important observation was that the organic modification of the zeolite surface did not improve their sorption properties in most petroleum products with exception of engine oil. Possible explanation could be found in the assumption that the surface modification improves sorption properties for organic liquids with high viscosity, such as motor oils since reduced zeolite's surface limits the access to the pores. The durability of the unmodified zeolite Cp was evaluated by regeneration using burning of the sorbed oil. It was demonstrated that it can be re-used up to 10 times in each sorption-combustion-sorption cycle keeping the properties of Cp.

Similar research was conducted by Carmody et al. (2007) involving different reference sorbents (mineral and natural organic - milled wood, cellulose, zeolite, sand as granules and/or powders), and organo-clays (montmorillonite and bentonite modified with octadecyltrimethylammonium bromide - ODTMA and dodecyldimethylammonium bromide - DDDMA) for sorption of DSC, HSC, and ESC — diesel, hydraulic oil, and engine oil hydrocarbon, respectively. The procedure of sorption capacity (SC) determination was based on the ASTM F726-99: Standard Test Method for Sorbent Performance of Adsorbents. The hydrocarbon SC obtained for ODTMA modified organo-clay is 7.2 g/g for diesel, 2.2 g/g for hydraulic oil to 2.1 g/g for engine oil, while DDDMA modified organo-clay resulted in SC of 5.2 g/g for diesel and 3.6 g/g for hydraulic and engine oil. These results surpassed the 1.9 g/g reported in literature for organoclays and the 0.6 g/g for zeolite.

Seifi et al. (2011) also utilised quaternary ammonium salts for modification of natural zeolite clinoptilolite and its corresponding granulated surfactant-modified natural zeolite nanoparticles to study the absorption of benzene, toluene,

ethylbenzene, and xylenes as a method of treatment of contaminated water. As an additional optimisation, the zeolite was milled mechanically to fine particles with average size (590–840 µm) and subsequently treated with two cationic surfactants - hexadecyltrimethylammonium chloride (HDTMA-Cl) and n-cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB). The prepared adsorbents were tested against BTEX from contaminated water. The system was designed for a single component model solution at initial concentration of 9 mg/L for each and the experiments were carried out at 20 °C while the contact time was varied in 0.5–72 h range. It was demonstrated that the granulated natural zeolite nanoparticles modified with cationic surfactant, possess higher ability to adsorb BTEX, as well as faster adsorption kinetics (i.e., 8 h) in comparison to natural non-granulated adsorbents (i.e., 24 h). Another difference, visible from the data obtained, is that adsorbents modified by CPB show higher adsorption capacity compared to the HDTMA-modified adsorbents following the order: benzene > toluene > ethylbenzene > xylenes. The data that described accordingly the kinetics of the adsorption process obeyed the pseudo-second-order kinetic model (three surface reaction models) where sorption is controlled by a chemisorption process and two intra-particle diffusion models (Weber and Morris and Vermeulen models).

A general problem of the adsorption method is the secondary pollution related to the further disposal and utilisation of organically modified materials, as well as the risks associated with the toxicity of quaternary ammonium salts (Sarkar, et al., 2013).

Another approach to modify the zeolites and to enhance their effectiveness as adsorbents is to load the zeolites with bacteria. Mirsalami et al. (2024) found that expanded zeolite incorporated with oil-degrading microorganisms mitigated the petroleum pollution.

Synthetic zeolites

Natural zeolites are abundant and inexpensive, but they show limited potential as sorbents for organic compounds without further modification. Unlike them, synthetic zeolites have demonstrated much better perspective compared to the adsorbents used to treat oil-contaminated waters (Bandura et al., 2015; Muir and Bajda, 2016) confirming their superior efficiency compared to the adsorbents used on a large scale (Vidal et al., 2012.; Szala et al., 2015).

The general route for the preparation of synthetic zeolites usually incorporates chemical reaction between silica (SiO₂), and an alumina (Al₂O₃) in basic solution, by varying different reaction parameters like temperature, pressure and reaction time. Initially pure chemical reagents were utilised in the process, but it turned to be very expensive and inapplicable, so alternatives were sought after. Raw minerals containing silica and alumina like clays, kaolin etc. proved to be reasonable alternative applied in the hydrothermal synthesis. Fly ash and clay minerals have been studied recently as raw materials in the zeolites' synthesis (Shams et al., 2013; Wdowin et al., 2014; Franus et al., 2015; Liu, 2022; Koshlak, 2023). The synthesis is usually conducted under high temperature and pressure to increase the crystallinity of the resulting zeolite.

Vidal et al. (2012) studied the effect of modification of synthetic zeolite Y, synthesised from kaolin, with hexadecyltrimethyl ammonium (HDTMA) as a surface modifying cation. Three samples of surfactant-modified zeolites

were prepared, with amounts of HDTMA corresponding to 50 %, 100 %, and 200 % of the total cation-exchange capacity (CEC) of the synthetic zeolite Y, respectively. The prepared samples were tested in removal of BTEX from aqueous solutions. The effects of the HDTMA loading level, adsorption kinetics, adsorption isotherms and adsorbent recoveries were studied. Based on the experimental results, it was concluded that for surfactant-modified zeolites (SMZ) the most efficient modification was with surfactant levels achieved at 100 % of CEC (to obtain SMZ-100 modified zeolite) for removal of BTEX from aqueous solutions. Kinetics studies, conducted on the multi-component BTEX model system adsorption, showed that equilibrium was reached within 6 h at 28 °C and followed pseudo-second-order kinetics. The contact time ranged from 30 min to 48 h and the BTEX concentration was 10 mg/l for each compound. The Langmuir, Freundlich, Redlich-Peterson and Temkin models were used to describe the BTEX adsorption capacity by SMZ-100. The BTEX initial concentration for each compound was in the range 2–60 mg/l and 12–360 mg/l for multi-component solution in the isotherm study. Temkin isotherm was found to be suitable for all BTEX compounds in a multi-component system pointing to indirect adsorbate-adsorbate interactions. Adsorption capacity of SMZ from the multi-component BTEX system was determined as follows: 12.13 mg/g for benzene, 13.75 mg/g for toluene, 13.86 mg/g for ethylbenzene, 13.98 mg/g for o-xylene, and 13.98 mg/g for m- and p-xylene and it was significantly lower for unmodified zeolite. The adsorption capacities followed the order: m-, p-xylene > o-xylene > ethylbenzene > toluene > benzene, likewise in other papers. Experiments on the possible regeneration of the HDTMA-zeolite Y were performed by heating the sorbent at 100 °C for 6 h, followed by a new adsorption cycle (up to 5 times). The results have shown that the sorption efficiency was at the same level after regeneration and that the adsorbent could be used efficiently in four adsorption cycles, except for benzene for which the sorption efficiency has been reduced after the first regeneration cycle. The experiment on loaded zeolite regeneration is of utmost importance because it indicated that both treatment costs and waste generation could be decreased.

Szala et al. (2015) reported the preparation of zeolite Na-P1 from fly ash and its subsequent modification with HDTMA in amounts of: 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 of external cation exchange capacity (ECEC) of Na-P1 at room temperature (20 °C) and a low solid/solution ratio (1:2). The sorption properties of surfactant modified zeolites towards benzene, toluene and xylene were estimated through experiments at room temperature (20 °C) at different initial concentrations. The results indicated that modification by HDTMA of Na-P1 benefits the sorption properties based on the initial concentration of benzene, toluene and xylene (50, 100, 250 mg/l), the sorption capacities varied from about 1.38 to 11.47 mg/g. An interesting observation was that HDTMA increased the sorption capacity for benzene and toluene but not that of xylene, which was the highest of all listed. The best working parameters were determined to be HDTMA-Na-P1 with loading level of 1.0 ECEC resulting in improvement of the sorption capacity of Na-P1 in terms of BTX compounds (benzene, toluene, xylenes) by several per cent. Experiments demonstrated the possibility to remove more than 95 % of toluene and xylene and more than 85 % of benzene contaminants from aqueous solutions.

The sorption of the different BTEX compounds is not the same but, in most studies, followed the order xylenes >

ethylbenzene > toluene > benzene (Vidal et al., 2012). The factors affecting this series order are various and governed by different molecular characteristics like molecular weight of the adsorbates, their hydrophobicity, water solubility, the size and geometrical shape of adsorbate particles, and the type of functional groups and viscosity. General consideration is that higher molecular weight adsorbates with larger sizes are more preferably adsorbed. The opposite trend was observed by Seifi et al. (2011) who demonstrated that the functionalisation of the surface of mineral adsorbents by surfactants could lead to improvement of the efficiency of BTEX sorption from aqueous solution. Different loading levels of surfactant lead to various sorption efficiency, the optimal loading level being 1.0 – 2.0 of CEC. It was observed that higher loading level hindered sorption efficiency.

Bandura et al. (2015) described the sorption of two diesel fuels and used engine oil by two synthetic zeolites Na-P1 and Na-X derived from fly ash, by natural clinoptilolite and commercial sorbent Absodan. It was determined that synthetic zeolites had around two times higher sorption capacity than Absodan, while the clinoptilolite sorption capacity was the lowest. The values obtained for Na-P1 were around 0.91 g/g, for Na-X around 0.79 g/g, for Absodan - 0.52 g/g, and for clinoptilolite - 0.36 g/g of used engine oil adsorbed by the corresponding adsorbent. The sorption process itself seemed to be mainly physical and was mainly defined by mesopore filling, so particle size distribution and sorbents texture were the factors for petroleum products immobilisation and higher sorption capacities were determined for oils with higher densities.

Although the surface of larger pores (mesopore surface area) affects strongly oils' sorption capacity, the BET specific surface area does not show significant effect on the oils' sorption. Synthetic zeolites possess two times higher oil sorption capacities compared to the other two sorbents. Synthetic zeolites obtained from fly ash proved to be a promising alternative for natural mineral sorbents for land-based petroleum spills cleanup and fine example of utilising waste product to generate valuable zeolites.

When comparing sorbents, the lowest values of sorption capacities were obtained for diatomite, zeolite Y and smectite modified by HDTMA, while the most efficient adsorbents were montmorillonite modified with PEG and zeolite Y modified with HDTMA. Most presented research revealed that sorption kinetics of organic compounds adsorption followed the mechanism of pseudo-second order model with a lot of time required to reach the equilibrium.

Zeolite composites

Zeolites continue to be subject of interest and are in the scope of the researchers, broadening the horizon with new perspectives for application (Mokrzycki, 2023; Kordala et al., 2024; Lang et al, 2024). A logical approach would be to combine the advantageous features of zeolites with other materials, so that the resulting composite would demonstrate the synergetic advantages of both components.

Bandura, et al. (2021) presented the compelling possibility to prepare zeolite-carbon composite *in situ* utilising high-carbon fly ash (HCFA) as a starting material in a simple one-step preparation method. The developed hydrothermal synthesis allows large scale production resulting in the formation of two types of composite materials: gismondite

(NaP1) and faujasite (NaX) zeolite onto the surface of carbonaceous matrix. Employing various methods for analysis, the structure and composition of the composites were clarified. They exhibited high content of carbon (28.1–44.5 %) and high percentage of silica and alumina (18.2–30.2 % and 10.0–13.6 %, respectively). The composites demonstrated well-defined zeolite crystals located onto the surface of the carbon component, that show better developed surface in comparison to HCFA. It was estimated that the specific surface area S_{BET} of high-carbon fly ash was 46 m²/g, and for the composite materials (NaP1-C and NaX-C) it was found to be 249 and 67 m²/g, respectively.

The scope of the study was to evaluate the possibility of using obtained zeolite-carbon composites for treatment of spills of petroleum substances in water so their sorption capacity toward oils was assessed. Two commercially available on the market products - engine oil of 5W-40 type (Magnatec) and kerosene (Sigma-Aldrich), as well as spent engine oil of 10W-40 type (Mobil), were used in the experiments. Engine oil is a mixture of hydrocarbons and additives, while kerosene consists mainly of C12-C15 aliphatic hydrocarbons. The density and kinematic viscosity of engine oil are higher than that for kerosene (at 40 °C 0.864 g/cm³ and 75 mm²/s, and 0.782 g/cm³ and 20 mm²/s, respectively). These are important parameters to consider as a clear dependence toward oil characteristics was observed by Muir et al. (2016). The average size and size distribution of the grains of HCFA and NaX-C composite are close while NaP1-C has smaller grains: 65.8 μm, 59.4 μm, 35.5 μm for HCFA, NaX-C and NaP1-C, respectively.

The adsorption capacity of the composites was estimated as mass of the substance per mass of the sorbent (g/g) by weighing the samples before and after their complete saturation. The data obtained from the experimental setup showed that the sorption capacity towards oils was as follows: 1.14–1.39 g/g for HCFA, 1.1–1.54 g/g for NaX-C, 1.32–1.69 g/g for NaP1-C. These results could be explained by the structural characteristics of materials and their physical-chemical properties. The highest sorption capacity was demonstrated by NaP1-C due to its smaller grain size, highest carbon content, the highest average pore diameters and total volume of pores. The results regarding the type of oil showed that the engine oil is adsorbed at the highest degree (except for HCFA) and kerosene at the lowest for all type of sorbents. These values for SC of the newly prepared zeolite-composite place them at the top of the list of the most effective adsorbents for the oil spills in the group of mineral adsorbents.

Mokrzycki et al. (2023) also investigated the possibility to use waste fly ash to prepare zeolite composites by implementing low (with the addition of vermiculite) and high contents of unburned carbon fly ash as a starting material for the following composites: zeolite + vermiculite (NaX-Ver) and zeolite + carbon (NaX-C). In order to properly estimate the sorption capacity of the composite material, their corresponding counterparts were prepared initially from waste fly ash with a low content of unburned carbon - the zeolite NaX-FA (fly ash zeolite NaX) was used as a reference.

The above listed materials were tested as sorbents for polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) as a component of petroleum contaminants. The tests were carried out in mixed n-hexane/acetone, 1:1 (v/v) media and deuterated phenanthrene-d₁₀ as an internal standard, when the samples were analysed by GC-MS.

It was established that content of PAHs adsorbed was dependent not only on the type of the composite but also on the number of aromatic rings present in the molecule. The highest sorption capacity (36.11 mkg/g) was demonstrated by the NaX-C composite which could be related to the high content of carbon within the raw material (HCFA). The trend of the sorption capacity of the zeolite composites could be summarised in the following order: NaX-Ver < NaX-FA < NaX-C. Regarding the trend for the number of condensed rings in the molecules of PAHs it is clearly visible from the data that 4-membered rings are adsorbed at much higher degree compared to the PAHs with lower and greater number of rings which is probably not the optimal result since PAHs with higher molecular weights (5- and 6-rings) are considered to be most harmful and carcinogenic compared to low molecular weight PAHs. The study demonstrated the opportunity to utilise waste material (fly ash) to produce valuable materials for removal of pollutants from wastewater which is in the scope of the circular economy goals.

Conclusions

Reported studies show that various oil polluted wastewaters can be treated with zeolites. The chemical properties of zeolites make them an excellent material that can be successfully used both in laboratory-scale systems, and in the industrial processes for solution of various environmental problems. Different types of zeolites - natural, modified with organic compounds, synthetic and composite materials were applied for removal of petroleum compounds such as phenols, BTEX, engine oils, etc. Growing importance of zeolites implies both investigation and search for new synthetic approaches, as well as improvement of their sorption capacity by surface modification and combination of zeolites with other materials.

A comparison in structure and properties of different types of zeolites may give insight into their applications. Natural zeolites have a low cost and are easily available but do not demonstrate good sorption characteristics toward petroleum products, while organic-modified ones show greater sorption capacity. Along with the indisputable advantages, there are certain limitations in the use of unmodified synthetic zeolites produced from industrial waste as they demonstrate moderate ability for sorption of oil spills. In contrast, modified natural and synthetic zeolites are more expensive, but relatively more effective. The synthetic zeolites are promising in terms of high removal degree of BTEX and even though their production is more expensive compared to the other types, the opportunity to utilise waste materials like fly ash makes them attractive alternative.

Zeolite composites showed superior sorption capacity (compared to the other zeolite materials) towards petroleum compounds. In some composites, the utilisation of fly ash as a raw material in the synthesis of sorbents is very beneficial. It is in accordance with the sustainable development and the clean production strategy ("green deal") aiming to reduce the quantity of generated high carbon fly ash waste.

The limiting factor for application of zeolites is the possibility for regeneration of waste from oil-loaded zeolites, since they are hazardous and could pose a threat for the environment. Disposal of modified zeolites could be problematic, due to the risks related to the toxicity of quaternary ammonium salts. Some authors report possible regeneration of the used organo-mineral adsorbents by

thermal treatment without significant effect on the sorption efficiency.

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